

Quality of service and its effect on stakeholder's relationships in the Office of the Security and Safety Group of X University

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Date Submitted: March 21, 2014

Date of acceptance: June 30, 2014

Through the years, the functions of the office of Security and Safety Group have evolved from the position of a general security and safety measures to protect the University community from physical harm, damage, theft and exposure to nuisance, possible immoral and illegal activities, and associations. For having huge responsibilities for exercising the general security in the University to ensure that its functions are within the scope of the general rules and regulations. The demand is a strategic and ethical management that aims to improve the efficiency in the day-to-day operations of the Security and Safety office which is quite a difficult task for the personnel. The study used descriptive method which is designed and enabled the researches to describe or present the picture of phenomena under investigation. Descriptive research focuses on individual subjects and goes into great depth and detail in describing them that contains knowledge about past or present activities of producing or using a service but does not much help for modifying it to correspond better to latest requirement. The findings of the study show that the SSG office of the University of the Visayas should restore a structural organization and functions based on the proposal for improvement and should align with the philosophy and mission of the institution. All the personnel should be oriented about them extensively and sincerely.

Keywords: *damages, nuisance, physical harm, safety, theft*

I. INTRODUCTION

The quality of service is quite playing a vital role in the development of organization. The development depends to some extent on the efficiency and effectiveness of work and training of the employees. Most employees of organization are comfortable of performing their job without following a documented

procedure or instruction. They find it easier to work without filing forms, making records or preparing reports. This might be an easy way of working, but does it really benefit them? Does this short-term convenience improve efficiency, reduce operating costs, or increase long-term benefits?

Through the years, the functions of the

office of Security and Safety Group have evolved from the position of a general security and safety measures to protect the University community from physical harm, damage, theft and exposure to nuisance, possible immoral and illegal activities, and associations. For having the huge responsibilities for exercising the general security in the University to ensure that its functions are within the scope of the general rules and regulations. In the pursuit of its functions, the office of Security and Safety Group intend to strictly (1) implement the University policies on wearing of school uniform and ID to ensure at least 90 % of the students comply with the requirements; (2) ensure the presence of at least 90 to 100 % SSG personnel rendering 8 hours of daily duty and leave the post only when there is a substitute any from the SSG personnel; (3) resolve at least 80 % of the incidents that happened inside the campus which are promptly reported; (4) apply supervisory authority through the Chief Security Officer directing to its uniform and civilian members of the group to implement the safety and security within the premises; (5) help preserve and maintain peace and order of the school and in protection of students, faculty, staff, administrative officials including the physical plant and property of the institution; (6) evaluate, review and monitor regularly the security, safety and emergency response unit to ensure continual efficacy, thus, regular emergency drills are conducted; and (7) keep the University sheltered with protection at all times, as the basic mandate among all.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMWORK

The evolution of the function of the office of Security and Safety Group has created so much impact insofar as requirements and expectation of the office of Security and Safety Group today are concerned. It is now regarded as responsible for securing, updating and maintaining the peacefulness of the University. Expectations of the students, faculty, staff, administrative

officials and other clientele are rapidly increasing that the office of Security and Safety has to stretch its limits to provide them with the best service possible in support of the mission-vision of the institution. In order to attain this vision, Security and Safety Group should be able to provide a safe workplace in order to minimize if not prevent the occurrence of accident in its facilities which could be a cause of many losses and could undermine the safety, reliability, and quality of its service.

To attain the goal of preventing incidents by keeping a safe working environment, Security and Safety Group started implementing industrial safety R.A. 5487 or Private Security Agency law which regulates the organization, operation business and activities of private detective, watchman or security guard agencies in the Philippines, states that Security Education is very important. The exposure and teaching of the employees on security and its relevance to their work is highly-recommended. Plant security is everyone's concern, and to be effective, employees cooperation and participation are required.

That in its facilitated in the early 1960's known as UV police. When Security and Safety Group started its formal safety program, the guidelines in implementing the safety program were just continued in circulars. These circulars were issued in a hodgepodge manner, i.e. these were issued only when the need arises. Each of these circulars was for a specific act only. In view of the forgoing, the primary objectives of a Security and Safety Group program, is attaining and maintaining a safe work place. A safe workplace does contribute a lot in the reduction of the number of accidents. The number accidents and the corresponding losses reflect the level of safety of the institution. The safety program should be comprehensive enough to preclude the unsafe acts and safe act conditions in the institution. Determining how comprehensive and how adequate

safety program poses a challenge both to the management and the employee. According to the management Peter Drucker (2005), the basic task of management is two folds:(a) marketing and (b) innovation. It means that through a quality service approach to management clearly stresses client satisfaction, employee involvement and innovation. In this approach, all employees contribute to the management and quality of their own output and, thus the success of the organization. Strong growing evidence suggests that a quality approach to management can yield dramatic results.

For having a huge responsibility of implementing the general security of the university. This demands a strategic and ethical management that aims to improve the efficiency in the day-to-day operations of the Security and Safety office which is quite a difficult task for the personnel.

In addition to the difficult task which constitutes in efficiency of services, there

are behavioral constraints, which according to David Nadler and Edward Lawler (2001), behavior is determined by a combination of factors in the individual and in the environment that individual decides between alternative that will lead to a desired outcome. For this reason, organization must need to employ development strategies on how to actuate personnel behavior for better services. It is our true hope that if this study supports the significant interplay of the work values and services committed, then it is the intention to come with an innovative program to the administration for appropriate implementation. The office of Security and Safety Group should strive to actuate an environment that promotes harmony and peace. They should seek to deliver quality service that is courteous, efficacious, and prompt. We are concerned for the development intervention to strengthen the service commitment of the office of University of the Visayas Security and Safety Group.

Figure 1. The schematic diagram

The most complex element of a value resides within the quality component for a company. Thus, quality is merely what it is that makes a product or service “worse”. Definitely, clienteles are attentive to literal qualities of the product or service but they are also interested on how that product will be delivered. The point is that satisfaction is not only about focusing largely on product element but also includes those issues that are influenced by a company’s channel system (Reidenbach & Goeke, 2005).

Satisfaction could also be viewed as the clientele’s feeling about the value which is communicated to the clientele then should cover what should be delivered to its clientele. In this way, clientele satisfaction tells an organization how well clienteles feel that anticipated values. These are driven by quality spectacles and therefore drive satisfaction in return are communicated through advertisement. According to Dodds (2003), consistent quality services given to the clienteles are the total experience of what clienteles receives for what they pay, thus considered as the value equation.

To satisfy clients immediately with regard to documents needed, these are promising practices for administrative such as, creating and enhancing data based on students via web-based system to track aid types, introduce a continues enrollment policies, which serve as the students to stay on track and work collaboratively with their mentors toward their final goal of completely the degree (Council of Graduates, 2008).

Miles and Snow (1972) and Bryson (1988) advocated that certain leaders should opt for an incremental process of change because the leaders responded only when needs and opportunities became clear and unequivocal. The final version reflects extensive consultation with employees. It now reflects the basic principles we all want to follow in delivering quality services. Delivering relevant, responsive, accessible and affordable quality services is

not an easy task given today’s environment of discerning citizens’ fiscal’s restraints and downsizing. However, based on the federal public service international reputation for excellence, the many departmental success to date, and the international reputation for excellence, the many department successes to date, and the enthusiasm with which public service employees are working to improve the delivery of services.

This overview to the quality services series of guides establishes a context for adopting a quality service approach in management. Building on departmental successes to date, these guides will provide, where available examples, references and best practices. We plan to add other guides to the quality services series, which you can use as tools to plan for action. In fact, we are currently working in two additional guides: (a) a guide to quality services in a regulatory environment; and (b) a guide to identify and interact with the many client groups serve by the public sector.

Design is what Simon (1969), and Nadler and Hibino (1990) contended in the process of responding to a problem. It tends to be narrow rather than comprehensive; it does not negate the assessment and reformation of criteria to determine program effectiveness in planning. Quality service organizations instead ask their clients while managing their expectations; supporting active employee involvement in meeting those needs; improving employee innovations and processes continuously; cultivating a “people first” environment where teamwork is valued; accepting the risk associated with innovations; support a continuous learning environment; and providing visible leadership for employees which is crucial to the success of any quality services initiative.

Leaders in quality service organizations ensure that clients’ needs and expectations are identified and managed, and they measure how

employees' suggestions geared improvements. Leaders create a quality services culture by ensuring that system needs to meet departmental or government wide policies are in place; that these systems reflect the goals and values of quality improvement; that appropriate feedback mechanisms such as those that encourage upward feedback, and improvement suggestions are in place; and that appropriate accountability measure such as effective performance agreement and appraisals are used. This focus on internal structure is crucial, as the organizations are able to provide quality services to external clients which depend on the quality of the organizations internal services delivering structure.

Owen (1995) also said that quality requires a trained workforce, and the assessment and meeting of their training needs are vital for success. Personnel of human resource is responsible for implementing and delivering a positive training policy that aims to develop the employees for the operation and growth of the business.

In most organization, process operations are controlled by people who have been specifically trained to undertake the works. These may not need written instruction in such cases. Training may eliminate the need for written instructions, but the manner in which competence of personnel is established must still be defined (Hodgskinson, 1997).

According to Sack (1997), long detailed work instructions, data sheets, equipment operating instructions, checklists, process records, lots and cost of paper works are not a requirement.

Responsibility for quality starts at the top. The executives of the organization have to take or board the responsibility for quality. To make it happen they have to define their policy, be committed to it and be involved in making it happen. Top management has to show all employees that they take quality

seriously. For this to happen, it is vital that communication is efficient, in placed and seen to be operating, and that management shows they place quality first. It is no good just talking about it, it is necessary to show that you mean it, are committed to it and are involved in achieving it. Agreeing and describing a clear chain of concerned have, for many companies, been one of the most significant benefits of ISO 9000 (Patterson, 1995). It frequently leads to more efficient use of existing resources and provides an opportunity to measure the real effectiveness of management. Anyone entering the Security and Safety Group office for the first time gains an immediate impression of the general atmosphere, culture, or ethos in which SSG personnel and staff work. Simon (2002) pointed out that the sense of atmosphere, or psychosocial context, cannot be separated from the physical environment—building, classrooms, shops, laboratories, studios, offices, grounds, and so on. The initial impression gained will undergo considerable modification as the supervisor observes the school in operation and as subsequent visits are made. The supervisor will discern both the formed and informal organization arrangement and interaction, and may begin to find specific patterns of behavior, interaction, and evidence. Moreover, the school cannot be understood apart from the community and the wide culture in which in functions.

In receiving the research on quality service, Anderson (2003) noted the many gaps and the nuclear evidence concerning the interaction of variables to create positive clientele outcomes. Nevertheless, she concluded on a positive note that despite the often confusing array of findings and methods in the research for quality services, the picture that emerges is beginning to take on destruct features. Certain characteristics of life are recurring in the research in association with both climate and outcomes. Alexander (1985) had pointed out; the trouble of implementing planned

change arises from one or a combination of these problems:

"...inadequate leadership, failing to see major problems that can block or delay action, poor condition of implementation activities, lack of skill in individuals who carry out the implementation, lack of logistical support, and lack of political will to accept and initiate change."

In order for this to happen, the perception and interpretation of management must jibe with the thinking as Hollnsteiner (1993) said:

"Before people can change, they must first be able to think about it within their own minds and then be able to talk about it with others, this is the time when management must start the reorientation process."

To be realistic, it should undergo certain stages ones perceived performance gaps have been identified. The transforms, i. e., the planned change method, the solutions, and consequences are immediately identified. Strategies, policies, and plans describe the distinct planned change effort that is undertaken at the SSG office. As a result of this, the strategy is depicted as the key idea (Ansoff, 1994) that captures the activities of planned change in a comprehensive manner. It emerges from a stream of choices made by key people in the SSG office and supported by Academic and Administrative divisions of the University. Theory of service means knowledge of what is permanent and normal in producing a service, traditionally, this knowledge has been accumulated in tacit form in the professional skills of the people involved in the act but today more and more of it is being documented in writing by researchers.

II. The Study

The main aim of the study was to determine

the quality of service and its effect on stakeholder relationship in the office of Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas.

More specifically the following sub-problems are raised:

1. What is the profile of the personnel of Security and Safety Group?;
2. What is the quality of service offered by the office of Security and Safety Group?;
3. What extent does the office of Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas maintains harmonious relationships?;
4. What are the problems encountered in the office of Security and Safety Group in connection with the performance of the aforementioned services and with the corresponding extent of service?; and
5. What proposal may be designed based on the findings of the study?

III. Methods

The study uses the descriptive method of research which designed and enabled the researchers to describe or present the picture of phenomena under investigation. Descriptive research focuses on individual subjects and goes into great depth and detail in describing them that contains knowledge about past or present activities of producing or using a service but does not much help for modifying it to correspond better to latest requirement.

Quality thereby is a clientele-preferred performance and functions which are also dependable and reliable. Quality as Yang (2000) noted, is only a part of value never less, it is a subjective term that has a physiological component. Overall clientele opinion of a quality of a particular product or service is called the perceived quality which is regarded as a better indicator of clientele values. Perceived quality is the foundation of their satisfaction; hence, poor quality equates to dissatisfaction. The descriptive theory was substantiated by the documentary analysis method because existing records were

perused to identify the respondents, to enrich the study and help in the analysis of data. The questionnaire was used as an instrument of data collection.

Environment. We conducted the study in the office of Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas ,Cebu City.

The University of the Visayas was the first school to be held as first university in Cebu. In the early 1960's they facilitated what we called UV police. When Security and Safety Group started its formal program, the guidelines in implementing the safety program were just continued in circulars. These circulars were issued in a hodgepodge manner; i.e. these were issued only when the need arises. The determination of quality of service and its effect on stakeholder's relationship will be documented in the area.

Sample/Participants. We approached potentials respondents through the help of the dean and head of Security and Safety Group. The respondents were: (1) students ;(2) faculty; and (3) administrators in the University of the Visayas.

Table 1. Respondents of the study

Respondents	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Students	70	70 %
Faculty	20	20 %
Administrators	10	10 %
Total	100	100 %

Instrument. The questionnaire was used as an instrument of data collection and contains four parts:

Part 1 contains questions regarding the profile of the personnel of the Security and Safety Group University of the Visayas;

Part 2 contains questions regarding the assessment of the quality of services delivered within the office of Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas. Each question of this part is followed by a number of responses corresponding

to each response are numeric scales with the following qualitative equivalents:

- 5 - Excellent (E) means that from 81 % to 100 % the service;
- 4 - Very Good (VG) means that from 61 % to 80 % the service of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectation in half of the cases;
- 3 - Good (G) means that from 41 % to 60 % the services of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectation in half of the cases;
- 2 - Fair (F) means that from 21 % to 40 % the services of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectations in a few cases; and
- 1- Poor (P) means that from 1 % to 20 % the services of the office of Security and Safety Group do not; in anyway, meet your expectations.

Part 3 contains questions regarding the assessment on the stakeholder's relationship within the office of Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas; the questions in this part are followed by a numbers of items. Corresponding to each item is numeric scale with the following qualitative equipments:

- 5 - Very Great Extent (VGE) means that from 81 % to 100 % the harmonious relationship of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectations in all cases;
- 4 - Great Extent (GE) means that from 61 % to 80 % the harmonious relationship of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectations in the majority of cases;
- 3 - Moderate Extent (ME) means that from 41 % to 60 % the harmonious relationship of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectations in a few cases;
- 2 - Less Extents (LE) means that from 21 % to 40 % the harmonious relationship of the office of Security and Safety Group meet your expectations in a few cases; and

- 1 – Never (N) means that the harmonious relationship of the office of Security and Safety Group does not; in anyway, meet your expectations.

Part 4 contains questions regarding the problems encountered in the office of Security and Safety Group in connection with the performance of the services and their corresponding extent of seriousness. Each question in this part is followed by a number of items. Corresponding to each item is numeric scale with the following qualitative equivalents:

- 5 – Very serious means that from 81 % to 100 % the problems encountered affect in all cases the clientele;
- 4 – Serious means that from 61 % to 80 % the problems encountered affect in the majority of cases the clientele;
- 3 – Moderately serious means that from 41 % to 60 % the problems encountered affect in half of the cases of clientele;
- 2 – Less serious means that from 21 % to 40 % the problems affect in half of the cases in the clientele of Security and Safety Group; and
- 1 – Not serious means that from 1 % to 20 % the problems encountered do not affect the clientele of the office of Security and Safety Group.

Part 5 contains a final question for the innovations which may be introduced in the office of Security and Safety Group. In the formulation process, the researchers used the 2007 Quality

Policy/ Objective and Procedures manual of regulation by Quality Management Review of University of the Visayas as the primarily source of information

Data Analysis. We collected the accomplished questionnaires and we processed the following: simple percentage was utilized to treat the gathered data regarding on the quality of services; clientele relationships of the Security and Safety Group office and the problems encountered in the performance of the functions and responsibilities of the SSG office; ranking was used to determine the relative positions of the values recommendations of the respondents based on priority; weighted mean was resorted to in order to make an appraisal of the degree to which the problems adversely affect the operations of the Security and Safety Group office in all cases; and the study of five-point scale to assess the quality of services delivered by the offices of SSG.

Procedure. We utilized convenience sampling in the determination of the respondents of the study. The respondents were the students, faculty and the administrators. They were selected according in their availability to visit the office of Security and Safety Group, on the other hand, the universal sampling was utilized in the case of the administrators.

The researchers personally asked for the approval of the administrator and university chief security officer through a letter duly endorsed by the researchers with the notification by the dean of College of Criminal Justice Education.

Fig 2. Conceptual paradigm

After the required authorization was secured, we presented the questionnaires to some faculty and students of the University of the Visayas. We requested some personnel of the office of Security and Safety Group to do the distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire.

The moment all the measuring data were already in the possession, we proceeded to statistically describe, collect, treat, analyze and interpret the result of the light of the rationale of the study. The researchers exerted every possible effort to produce an objective and logical narrative grounded on the finding of the statement. The weights assigned to the scale were taken into account. The weighted mean of each item was determined.

IV. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

It was deemed profitable to look into the profile of the personnel of the SSG office, University of the Visayas in order to have supplementary facts crucial to the in-depth analysis of the information provided by the respondents of the study. The study of Drucker (1909/ 2005) attested the basic task of the management has two folds: (a) marketing and (b) innovation. This point of view indicates that the profiles of the personnel and staff have some influence on the services rendered to the clientele.

We found out that majority of the personnel in the Security and Safety Group is currently connected in the Bachelor of Law. These personnel who are government employees from the different law enforcement agency rendered service in the SSG in exchange to their scholarship privilege. The foregoing data bear out the incontestable fact, that is, that the uniform personnel who belong at the Security and Safety Group at the University of the Visayas are endowed in high educational attainment. Based on data, the most common preparatory degree of the personnel during the years 2007-2010 is preferably Bachelor of Laws because most of the uniform personnel are a member of Philippine National Police (PNP) and through there schooling

it will soar up their position. This however, being interpreted based on their program covers varied subject of concentration. Each of these subjects of concentration requires a varying nature and level of educational qualifications. Taking anchor on this it can be said that how organization help their people achieve excellence, recruitment, planning, involvement, continuous learning, innovation empowerment, feedback, recognitions and rewards are key aspects of an environment that help employees reach their full potential. What determines the educational qualifications of the personnel in terms of academic preparations are not their highest educational attainment prior to their entry but the harmonization of their performance as member of the organization to their specific areas of concentration. But Owen (1995) also said that quality requires a trained workforce, and the assessment and meeting of their training needs are vital for success. Personnel of human resource are responsible for implementing and delivering a positive training policy that aims to develop the employees for the operation and growth of the business.

Civilian personnel play an important role in the office of Security and Safety Group. In fact, civilian personnel roles do not end in the school but extend beyond to outside school activities. Students, faculty, and administrators' relationships with SSG personnel are essential to successfully completing the harmonious relationship with each other. No one will argue that the desire and quest for civilian SSG personnel in attaining better services. They suffered sleepless nights and days. But, fueled and driven by their motivation to advance and grow individually and professionally, the SSG personnel stood undaunted. As expected, they did all that needs to be done. These SSG personnel gave whatever it takes. This "go for it" other known as "risk" attitude of SSG personnel ensured and secured for them their better services. SSG civilian personnel of the University of the Visayas are expected to maintain a grade of 2.5 or higher. As part of the schools commitment to quality education, the academic

performance of the SSG personnel is evaluated periodically with their performance on services as member of Security and Safety Group.

Based on data, the most common preparatory courses of civilian personnel are criminology and maritime students who show influencing factor in pursuing further education. This was being related based on their job description to their upcoming field of work. The office of Security and Safety Group emphasizing the service that related within the field of criminology, other factors that influenced the students into pursuing education are "family desire", scholarship grants and other factors that enlighten the personnel to continue in their services and the satisfaction in return are communicated through advertisement. According to Dodds (2003), consistent quality services that the service provides given to the clientele are the total experience of what clientele receives for what they pay, thus considered as the value equation.

The services and functions of the office designed to support and enhance the quality and integrity of services provided to the office of Security and Safety Group. Thus, Peters (2008) argued that consumer's perception of the quality of product of service is most important factor in determining its success. Quality as defined by consumer, he argued that price is determining demand for most good and services.

The foregoing data bear out the incontestable fact, that is, that the length of experience of uniform personnel of Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas stand as basis according to the degree year level of personnel that corresponds to the length of experience of services. The findings indicated that the Security and Safety Group, University of the Visayas have both efficient and competent police force in rendering services and tenured who have honed their working skills over the years. It is also noteworthy to emphasize that there are two of the uniform personnel who belonged to the longest length of service and experience in the Security

and Safety Group within the bracket of four years and above. The tenured personnel have been in their work place for quite some time and have known their co-employees already as member of Philippine National Police (PNP). This further indicated that most of the uniform personnel joined as working students and avail the scholarship privileges granted by the University of the Visayas. The length of time and experience does not determine the standard educational qualifications of the personnel but the harmonization of their performance as member of the organization to their specific areas of concentration but (Turner 2008), believed that time is very important to enhance more in occupying services.

In sure, perception of quality affects the feelings of satisfaction. Measuring quality and clientele satisfaction are undertaken to better understand how business may better understand and how to enhance clientele's value.

As the study revealed, the personnel of Security and Safety Group of the University of the Visayas have greatly influenced the performance of the SSG personnel, through there tactical trainings and services, personnel would learn and enlighten there mind in the future trainings of services. Security and Safety Group has helped the personnel in preparation with regards to the requirement of quality experiences. The same is true with regards to the matching up of the academic performance of the working students, since they are monitored by the Human Resource Development Management (HRDM), Security and Safety Group personnel would try hard to maintain the required grades to continue availing the privileges granted by the University of the Visayas. Going into the particular of the length of experience, same as those of uniform personnel, Security and Safety Group civilian personnel occupies the length of experience according to the length of degree year level as taken by them. They were serving as working student, rendering eighth hours of duty daily according to their job description. The Security and Safety Group,

University of the Visayas greatly influences the performance of the students as future policeman since majority of working student personnel of Security and Safety Group are criminology students.

The data from the study which are tabulated in table 5 lean to one interpretation, that is, enhancement for the development of quality services and motivation of personnel to finish their course as Owen (1995) also said that quality requires a trained workforce, and the assessment and meeting of their training needs is vital for success. Personnel of human resource are responsible for implementing and delivering a positive training policy that aims to develop the employees for the operation and growth of the business. At a glance on the preceding table, it is deliberately clear that the five functions rendered in the Security and Safety Group got a *good* assessment. Means to say, there is still much room for improvement especially as regards to the implementations of policies and guidelines that were taken for granted due to constraints in effort, methods, materials and manpower. Clarity of the tasks and procedures at hand pave the way for a better and clear execution of duties and responsibilities essential to the promotion of quality service.

The respondents attested that there were situations in which the SSG offices could not accomplished the scheduled date for the releasing of the documents. It is incredibly frustrating for them since they just came here to claim the documents and they are living outside Cebu City. Punctuality of service is demonstrated by the SSG personnel who committed their time to the individual and their transactions, but not in putting any unnecessary pressure on the individual to alter their schedule, can go a long way in the development of a great and prosperous working relationship.

The findings indicated that the personnel delineate their personal problems from their work. They see to it that there is continuity and

harmonious flow of their work in spite of their personal concerns.

Punctuality is a universal value in relation to any work place. The Security and Safety Group office must take a reasonable approach with this concept. Respondents claim that punctuality in the services rendered by the SSG office is vital as it shows respect. Punctuality at all times is paramount in any environment. It is you showing that the personnel and staff are responsible, disciplined, professional, well-organized, and above all and most important, respectful to their clientele. By running late on the transaction, it delays other concerns of the clientele. It also demonstrates time management and trust.

Clientele values employees who understand and possess a willingness to work hard. In addition to working hard, it is also important to value the time of the clientele. This means learning the most efficient way to complete tasks and to find ways in saving time while completing daily assignments. It is also important to care for the clientele and complete all requests while maintaining positive attitude. Clientele are the most important asset. They are the lifeblood of our business and their satisfaction is the ultimate objectives of all we do (Williams, 2006).

Employers value employees they can trust and who exhibit respect to the clientele. Much of the universal values and virtues that can contribute to the good of the individual and society and affirm our human dignity are derived from the value of respect. The value of respect is very important for the respondents in a way that the employees show appreciation for the worth of their clientele. The respondents attested that majority of the employees in the Security and Safety Group office show the value of respect and being thoughtful of showing regard for their clientele since we are all different, some of us come from different culture. There were cases in which the employees disregard this value. Some of the employees could not control their negative behavior by raising their voices when talking

to the clientele. One respondent claimed that "it is important for all of us to treat one another respectfully despite our differences, as we all have similar needs and feelings. Adian (2000) cited harmonious clientele relationship includes not only responding to their expectation but also helping and journeying with them, defining the educational goal developing greater effectiveness in services, building a productive organizational unit, creating a climate for growth, and searching for resources that makes the interaction alive and practical.

The most striking indicator is explaining the various options available to a particular query. The SSG personnel possessed an enduring attitude that a friendly and accommodating social climate prevails among people in the SSG office. This closely followed by adhering to the standards and expectations of the group to prevent conflict and argument. Findings showed that a smooth interpersonal relationship prevails in the workplace because the personnel have strong bonding and favorable social climate which fosters the spirit of friendliness, acceptance and teamwork.

The importance of implementation has sensed an increasing number of Security and Safety Group who feels that not much is being done by administration to fully make the impact of planned change on immediate necessity. Perhaps, as Alexander (1985) had pointed out, the trouble of implementing planned change arises from one or a combination of these problems: "Inadequate leadership; failing to see major problems that can block or delay action; poor condition of implementation activities and lack of skill in individuals who carry out the implementation."

The most salient indicator is provision of a prompt service in the clients. In this endeavor, the personnel exercise their promptness in adopting strategies that are clientele-oriented. This is more focused on the innovative working approaches which make the functions more efficient, effective and developed.

The respondents revealed that the personnel of the Security and Safety Group should act on the moment that they requested documents or credential. Being on time or being prompt is important because sometimes preparations are needed. The clients may be on tight schedule, and demonstrate responsibility that builds clients trust. Promptness is an important attribute to possess and practice in many different aspects of personal and professional life. Being prompt in one dealing gives warrant to opportunity and advancement. Prompt action is an effective way to take control of a situation or incident. When a situation is not approached in a prompt manner it can escalate to a point harder control. This would make an unnecessarily larger incident that may require more resources than originally predicted. There are many situations in the SSG office that require a prompt response. As related to the SSG office services, prompt response can be a determining factor of the degree of loss in the time and resources of the clientele. A prompt response is warranted and expected from the SSG office. The respondents claimed that the personnel have a responsibility to practice and apply this attribute in their delayed transactions. If there are situations in which the change of schedule of schedule delays are inevitable, proper information must be given to the clientele to save their resources and time. Being ready and punctual promote a strong self image that is projected to other individuals. The same can be said about the opposite. Not doing so can develop a bad reputation of the office. The study stated that efficiency is very vital in dealing with the clientele. This means producing productive effects. Being efficient means producing results with little wasted effort. It is the ability to carry out actions quickly. However, by so doing these involve achieving worthwhile goals and support the objectives of the SSG office. Majority of the respondents confirmed that efficiency is enhanced when the personnel take time to re-evaluate the specified work.

Clienteles seek employees who are adaptable and maintain flexibility in completing tasks in an ever changing workplace. Being open to change and improvement provide an opportunity to complete work assignments in a more efficient manner while offering additional benefits to the department, to the clienteles, and to the entire institution.

Efficiency is applicable to all organization functions including management or leadership, team building and employee performance, production, innovation, and all internal processes including those in the business office. Efficient personnel in the SSG office response on the request on time. An effective staff has a system in place that enables the SSG office to integrate input with the output in order to insure the least cost is incurred at all times. An efficient staff or process will perform as expected and operate in the short-term. They spend the expected output to produce results. But as Miles and Snow (1992) and Bryson (1988) advocated certain leaders should opt for an incremental process of change because the leader responds only when needs and opportunities become clear and unequivocal.

A positive attitude gets work done and motivates others to do the same without dwelling on the challenges that inevitably come up in the work place. It is the enthusiastic employee who creates an environment of good will and who provides a positive role model for others as Hollnsteiner, (1993) said, before people can change, they must first be able to think about it within their own minds and then be able to talk about it with others.

The problem of the implementation of "NO ID NO ENTRY" policy starts with the inconsistency of service rendered by the Security and Safety Group personnel as revealed by the respondents, some of the personnel do not know how to approach anyone while implementing the "NO ID NO ENTRY" policy. Some of the respondents revealed that the services rendered by the SSG personnel have preferential treatment in terms

of the implementation of the policy. In addition to this; the lack of personnel is also the main problem to attain better services. In view of this, Dodd (2003) pointed out that through consistent quality service, the service providers give to the clienteles the total experience of what clienteles receive for what they pay that is true value equation. That satisfaction could also be viewed as the clienteles feeling about the value that they received from a particular product experience. In this way, clienteles satisfaction tells an organization how well clienteles feel that their existing offers are performing relative to the goal. The respondents revealed the following consequences on this problem: inability to handle volume of tasks due to the use of manual procedures; problems of operations recur due to limited logistics; lack of systematic progress evaluation of tasks; unchecked backlogs; complaints of delay recurs; and occasional target setting not monitored regularly. Low productivity is often a problem that is brought about by a host of factors. In connection to the resolution of incident which are promptly reported, constraints may take place when problems already arise and the delayed of report occur. In such cases, problems would no longer solve due to the delayed evolvement of the problem. Going back to the quality, it is defined as the characteristic of a product or service that bear on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs and a product or service free of deficiencies. Quality thereby is a clientele-preferred performance and functions which are also dependable and reliable. Quality, Yang (2007) noted, is a part of value, not all of value. Nevertheless, it is a subjective term that has a psychological component. For instance, the higher the quality the higher the levels of satisfaction hence poor quality equates to dissatisfaction.

The inaccessibility of facilities and equipment, the willingness of the personnel to take immediate action, and the adequacy of personnel are the main problems of the study that may constantly occur resulting to ineffectiveness of services. As the

presentation of the table shows, it has been said that the problems encountered by the Security and Safety Group personnel in connection to the resolving like disasters/emergencies were absolutely occurred because facilities and equipment were not accessible and strategies, policies, and plans were not fully described by the effort that was undertaken at the Security and Safety Group. Thus, Ansoff (1994) noted, to be realistic, it should undergo certain stages once perceived performance gaps have been identified. The transforms, i.e. the planned changed effort that is undertaken at the Security and Safety Group office.

These findings of the study show that the SSG office of the University of the Visayas should restore a structural organization and functions based on the proposal for improvement should reflect in the philosophy and mission of the institution. All the personnel should be oriented about it extensively and sincerely.

V. CONCLUSION

On the profile of the personnel of Security and Safety Group, the educational qualifications of the uniform personnel were preferably Bachelor of Laws, and Bachelor of Science Criminology and Maritime students for the civilian personnel. On the length of experience of uniform personnel quadrant 3-4 claimed the greatest frequency while quadrant 1-3 asserted the greatest frequency for the civilian personnel.

On the quality of services offered by the SSG on the implementation of "NO ID NO ENTRY" policy, issuance of vehicle sticker passes, and resolution of incident which are promptly reported, the respondents affirmed a very good evaluation while on responsibilities during disaster and emergencies the respondents affirmed a good evaluation.

On the assessment of the stakeholder relationship of the SSG office, University of the Visayas, on the extent of courtesy, punctuality of service, respect, proper communication, and

promptness, the respondents affirmed a great extent evaluation while moderate extent for the efficiency of services.

The problems encountered by the office of SSG, in connection with the performance of the aforementioned services and with the corresponding extent of services. On the issuance of vehicle sticker passes, implementation of "NO ID NO ENTRY" policy, resolution of incident which are promptly reported and responsibilities during disasters/emergencies, the respondents affirmed that the SSG were serious in the problems encountered.

Proposal based on the findings

All of the constraints mentioned have an impact on the innovations in the SSG office, University of the Visayas –main campus. To achieve the innovations, a well trained, active personnel and programming development are advocated strongly. These are discussed in the succeeding section.

1. Good training must be introduced to the personnel;
2. It should be the employee who will transact the clients and not the working students;
3. Avoid people inside the office having no transaction ;
4. Personnel must be professional in a particular area;
5. Someone should be assigned as investigating officer;
6. More personnel for better services;
7. Someone should be assigned to double check the records to avoid erroneous entry of records; and
8. More equipment for better services.

Originality Index:	90 %
Similarity Index:	10 %
Paper ID:	470236574
Grammarly:	Checked

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